

Figure S2. Number of differentially expressed transcripts (DETs) with a fold-change greater than 2 (FC>2) identified in each pairwise comparison between embryos and megagametophytes. (A) Total number of up-regulated transcripts in embryos and megagametophytes (B) Number of up-regulated transcripts in embryos (orange) and megagametophytes (green) at different developmental stages during early seed development.

A

Tissue	DETs	DETs with GO annotation	TF DETs
Embryos	12,906	6,986	2,091
Megagametophytes	5,732	3,334	799
Total DETs	18,638	10,320	2,890

B

Figure S4. GO enrichment analysis of up-regulated transcripts (FC>2) in megagametophytes, identified in any of the pairwise comparisons between embryos and megagametophytes at the four developmental stages shown in Figure 1. Biological process enrichment was obtained using AgriGO Toolkit database (FDR < 0.05). High significant levels are represented by red squares.

